

Shrinkage in carbonatable binders: Are the cementitious standards applicable for non-hydraulic lime-cement systems?

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ABSTRACT

Recently approved regulations that aim to mitigate the release of greenhouse gases have been pushing the construction industry into reducing its carbon dioxide (CO₂) footprint. Therefore, promoting new low-carbon cements and carbonatable binders have been some of the strategies adopted. Lime has been trending as a green binder because it consumes less energy during production and due to the CO₂ capture during its hardening process. However, a new generation of binders demands a new generation of characterization standards. Given the absence of guidelines to measure the shrinkage of air lime-cement systems, the suitability of cementitious standards – ASTM C191:2021 (Vicat setting), ASTM C1698:2019 (autogenous shrinkage), and EN 12390-16:2019 (total shrinkage) – was addressed. Four mixtures were studied (C0L100, C33L67, C50L50, and C100L0). The first digit corresponds to the cement (CEM II/A-L 32.5R), and the second corresponds to the air lime (CL90S) content, both in the percentage of binder volume. Regarding the Vicat setting, the samples could be measured satisfactorily. On the autogenous shrinkage, the lack of interaction with CO₂ prevented lime carbonation, meaning limited hardening for those samples. Therefore, ASTM C1698:2019 was not suitable for lime-based materials. For the total shrinkage, EN 12390-16:2019 was suitable but complementary tests are needed to distinguish individual contributions (chemical, autogenous, and carbonation) to the total shrinkage. The results showed expansion for the groups with lime (especially for lime-cement, where lime acted as a catalyst). The expansion was associated with the carbonation of the unbounded portlandite. Finally, future studies should investigate chemical and carbonation shrinkage at early ages since the autogenous method was not capable of monitoring the volume instability of lime-based mortars.

KEYWORDS: *Air lime; carbon capture; cementitious standards; shrinkage.*

1. Introduction

Looking back to the past, it is impossible not to mention the construction works based on different processes using lime as a binder. Alvarez et al (1995) wrote about how Egyptians, Chinese, Mayans, Greek, Romans, and other civilizations relied on air and hydraulic lime for more than 7,000 years to promote infrastructure development in their societies. Every civilization empirically mastered the work with lime (as much as they could), and this expertise was spread and improved through the generations.

Lanas et al (2004) and Carran et al (2012) argue that the constant search for advances led Joseph Aspdin, in 1824, to come up with a ground-breaking alternative to lime binders: the Portland cement. The material that could set and develop strength faster, with more consistent behavior and better water-tightness capacity, quickly overtook the construction market. The overtake by the Portland cement has been solid enough to persist until today (Mehta and Monteiro (2006)). That said, lime – which was once widely employed as a building solution – has now been mostly limited to the conservation of the built heritage and masonry applications, as shown by Oliveira et al (2017) and Olaniyan (2020).

Despite the decaying trend for lime-based applications, the growing environmental concerns related to Portland cement have questioned its status quo. Hence, new sustainable alternatives have been studied, such

as supersulfated cement (Pinto et al (2020)), alkali-activated materials (Li et al (2021)), and lime itself (Olaniyan (2020)) – given its CO₂ absorption capacity and lower temperatures during production.

One might wonder about the relevance of studying lime since it dates several thousand years. Well, as briefly addressed before, all the expertise around lime was either empirical and got lost with time or has become obsolete with the industrialization of the lime production process. The Pyramids, Greek temples, and Roman monuments were most likely lime-based built (Alvarez et al (1995)), but we still do not know how. Therefore, to overcome this scenario, the chemical, physical, and mechanical characterization of lime has been the scope of several researchers in the past decades (Cizer et al (2012); Pavía and Brennan (2018); Vasović et al (2021)). However, one of the biggest problems that remain is the absence of standardized test protocols and replicable literature studies.

Thus, the objective of this paper is to raise awareness for the lack of standards in the characterization of lime-based materials. To do so, we assess the applicability of the standards available for cementitious binders focusing on the volume instability, more precisely, the shrinkage behavior of air lime-based materials. Understanding the shrinkage in lime-based materials is of fundamental relevance because this way, we can ensure that the durability and the structural integrity of new and historic buildings are not jeopardized in the short or long term due to volumetric changes.

2. Materials and Methods

The shrinkage behavior of four mixtures was monitored (C100L0, C50L50, C33L67, C0L100). The first (after C) and second (after L) digits correspond to the cement and lime volume contents (%), respectively.

2.1 Materials

The mortar mixtures were produced with hydrated air lime (type CL90S) and Portland cement with added limestone (CEM II/A-L 32.5R). Siliceous sand (granulometry 0 – 2 mm) and potable tap water was used in the mixtures. The chemical characterization of the binders is described in Table 1.

Table 1 - Chemical composition (%) of the binders determined by XRF

	CaO	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	SO ₃	MgO	K ₂ O	TiO ₂	Na ₂ O	Others ¹
Air lime	98.72	0.12	0.06	0.06	0.07	0.80	0.03	-	0.03	0.10
Cement	73.16	15.44	3.67	3.13	2.54	0.92	0.37	0.28	0.19	0.30

¹It may include negligible contents of P₂O₅, SrO, Cl, ZnO, MnO, BaO, ZrO₂, PbO, Rb₂O, and Y₂O₃.

Regarding the sand, the loose bulk density was 1.76 g/cm³, the specific gravity was 2.62 g/cm³, and the water absorption was 0.07 %. The mineralogical composition was determined by XRD (scan 5° - 75°, counting time per step 1.25 s, step size 0.020° 2θ), showing SiO₂ as the major compound. The mortars were designed following the 165 mm consistency recommended by EN 459-2:2021. The mixing procedure followed EN 196-1:2016. The mixture composition of the mortars is shown in Table 2.

Table 2 - Mixture details at the mortar level

Group	Cement (kg/m ³)	Lime (kg/m ³)	Sand (kg/m ³)	Water (kg/m ³)
C100L0	340	-	1677	252
C50L50	176	65	1741	248
C33L67	118	86	1742	256
C0L100	-	131	1760	265

2.2 Methods

This study addresses some of the available standards (i.e., ASTM C191:2021, ASTM C1698:2019, and EN 12390-16:2019) applicable to cementitious materials to characterize the shrinkage behavior in air lime-based systems cured according to EN 1015-11:2019. A brief description is stated in sequence.

- ASTM C191:2021 – Vicat setting: the “Method B” was chosen to determine the setting time (and as a requirement for the autogenous shrinkage test) because it is a relatively simple procedure. It uses equipment that is generally available in laboratories (favoring replicability), and it allows moisture and CO₂ exchange with the environment (thus, carbonation). Results are an average between two replicates. The setting was measured under (53 ± 1) % RH and (19 ± 1) °C. Results were treated statistically.

- ASTM C1698:2019 – Autogenous shrinkage: This approach allows measuring the shrinkage under isothermal conditions and no-moisture exchange even before demolding, which is relevant for lime-cement systems, since demolding takes place between 1-3 days (lime content < 50%, in mass) or 5 days (cement content < 50% in mass), according to EN 1015-11:2019. Results are an average between two replicates. Autogenous shrinkage was measured in sealed specimens at the mortar level up to 28 days after casting and under (53 ± 1) % RH and (19 ± 1) °C. Results were treated statistically.

- EN 12390-16:2019 – Total shrinkage: In this study, the total length change was measured considering the moisture, temperature, and CO₂ interaction. Results are an average between two replicates, measured up to 56 days after casting. After curing, specimens were stored under (53 ± 3) % RH and (19 ± 3) °C.

3. Results and Discussion

The setting times according to the ASTM C191:2021 and the results on the autogenous shrinkage measurements according to ASTM C1698:2019 are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3 - Final setting and autogenous shrinkage results

	Final setting (hours:minutes:seconds)	Autogenous shrinkage (µm/m)					
		0 days	1 day	3 days	5 days	7 days	28 days
C100L0	04:38:00	0.000	1.955	-3.713	-4.946	-7.754	-13.500
C50L50	08:37:43	0.000	1.698	-0.856	-0.778	-0.626	-2.875
C33L67	12:30:00	0.000	6.180	4.226	3.990	2.983	2.359
COL100	35:22:50	0.000	299.540	383.097	409.847	420.115	461.910

As seen in Table 3, the final set took longer for the mixtures with greater lime content, as expected. The slow setting in lime-based materials is associated with the limited availability of alumina and silicate phases (see Table 1). According to Cizer et al (2012), the setting of air lime relies on the drying of excess water (which might lead to shrinkage) and the carbonation (from the surface inwards). Thus, considering the results obtained and the data available in the literature, the ASTM C191:2021 proved to be a reasonable approach to measure the setting time of lime-based systems.

Regarding the autogenous shrinkage, given the sealed environment, no carbonation (hence, limited hardening) was expected within the lime-based groups. This behavior was confirmed, as seen in Table 3. The greater the lime content, the greater the expansion. This expansion does not necessarily represent a length increase but (most likely) the dissolution of Ca(OH)₂. This hypothesis agrees with Fourtentin et al (2015). In contact with water, the hydrated lime releases the Ca⁺² and hydroxyl ions. In contact with cement, it alters the precipitation and growth rate of C-S-H (leading to reassociation and shrinkage). A future investigation into the chemical shrinkage is needed to detail this behavior.

The total shrinkage is shown in Figure 1. While cement shrunk and lime-cement specimens expanded, pure lime specimens remained practically stable, proving that the lime-cement interaction caused the specimens to behave differently than the pure lime/cement ones.

Figure 1 - Progress of the total shrinkage

It is known that while the carbonation of calcium-based phases in cement leads to reassociation (and, thus, shrinkage), the calcium-based elements in lime are not as strongly bonded, and its carbonation promotes expansion (Li et al (2020)). This explains the behavior observed in Figure 1. In addition, Fourmentin et al (2015) showed that, in contact with cement, lime act as a catalyst, which explains the different behavior of the lime-cement groups. According to Fourmentin et al (2015), in lime-cement systems, lime-based precipitations usually happen in the cement pores (from the surface inwards). Thus, chemical and physical investigations on the pore structure are needed to confirm this theory.

4. Conclusions

The objective of this paper was to assess the applicability of cementitious standards to characterize the shrinkage behavior of lime-based systems. ASTM C191:2021 was adequate to measure the setting times. The sealed environment proposed by ASTM C1698:2019 did not provide insightful results. Instead, the chemical shrinkage might be a better parameter to assess the early age volume change in lime-based systems. Finally, the total shrinkage (EN 12390-16:2019) approach was reasonable, but the curing conditions established by EN 1015-11:2019 must be taken into consideration. Also, complementary tests are needed to distinguish the influence of different ongoing mechanisms, such as drying and carbonation.

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